

Capacity Building or Income Generation and Marketing of SHGs Product: A Study in Madurai District of Tamil Nadu

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Ramadevi, N. "Capacity Building or Income Generation and Marketing of SHGs Product: A Study in Madurai District of Tamil Nadu." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 155–63.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551398>

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Abstract

The main objective of this paper is to analyze the role and contribution of self-help groups in promoting income generation and marketing of SHGs products through capacity building among women in Tamil Nadu, especially in Madurai district. This paper also focuses on the role of NGOs in providing the skill training and development for the women SHGs to improve their livelihood. The training on selling and information technologies would decide the achievement of self-help group members. Self-help group have been playing a vital role in the practice of economic addition and women empowerment. It is in this context that this paper describes the capacity building strategies adopted by NGOs in Tamil Nadu, especially Madurai.

Introduction

Capacity Building or Capacity Development starts from the principle that people are best empowered to realize their full potential when the means of development are sustainable. UNDP has defined Capacity Development as the process through which individuals, organizations and societies obtain, strengthen and maintain the capabilities to set and achieve their own development objectives over time. The capacity building of Self-Help Group members through vigorous training plays an important role in empowering women and future sustainability of SHGs. Self-help group (SHG) is a group of 12 to 20 women of the same socio-economic background who come forward voluntarily to work together for their own upliftment. The unique feature of the SHG is its ability to inculcate among its members the viable habits of thrift, savings and banking. Regular savings, periodical meetings, compulsory attendance and systematic training are the salient features of the SHG concept. Each group selects one animator and two representatives from among themselves. The animator is responsible for providing leadership to the group and to maintain the various registers. The representatives assist the animator and maintain the bank accounts of the group, to which they belong. 1 It is in this context that this paper strives to analyze the role and contribution of self-help groups in promoting income generation and marketing of SHGs products through capacity building among women in Tamil Nadu, especially in Madurai district.

Concept of Self-Help Group

One of them main activities of the SHG is the establishment of groups and encouraging savings habits. Savings encourage people to plan for future needs. The group members participate in open discussions and think about various options. Such discussions help in strengthening the analytical and problem-solving skills of the women. Enterprising attributes are initiative, creativity, flexibility, leadership, independence, problem solving, persuasiveness, calculated risk taking, need for achievement, hard work and learning from mistakes.²

The Concept of SHG is Based on the Following Principles

- Self –help supplemented with mutual help can be a powerful vehicle for the poor in their socio-economic development;
- Participative financial services management is more responsive and efficient;
- Poor need not only credit support, but also savings and other services;
- Poor can save and are bankable and SHGs as clients, result in wider outreach, lower transaction cost and much lower risk costs for the banks;
- Creation of a common fund by contributing small savings on a regular basis;
- Flexible democratic system of working;
- Loaning is done mainly on trust with a bare documentation and without any security;
- Amounts loaned are small, frequent and for short duration;
- Defaults are rare mainly due to group pressure.³

In 1986-87, SHG was initiated by National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD), in 1991-92; the NABARD launched a pilot project to provide micro-credit by linking SHGs with banks. In 1992-93, 255 SHGs were linked to banks by NABARD which in turn provided the banks with a loan of Rs. 2.89 millions (as finance). SHGs were growing more in numbers chronologically as follows: 620 in 1993-94, 2,122 in 1994-95; 8,598 in 1996-97; 14, 317 in 1997-98; 179091 in 2004-05; 22, 38,565 in 2005-06; 29,24,973 in 2006-07; 50,09,794, in 2007-08.

Forty eight commercial banks, 192 Regional Rural Banks and 264 Co-operative Banks are associated with SHGs and bank-linkage programmes. This SHG programme has been operated in more than 523 districts in India. 2800 NGOs and other agencies are involved in this programme. It is noteworthy to see that statistically region-wise in the year 1998 that SHGs are dominantly functioning in southern region and its lion's share was 62 per cent.

Several states in India recorded a significant increase in the number of SHGs which were financed by banks. During the year March 2008, 10, 07,071, SHGs in Andhra Pradesh; 61,18,441 SHGs in Tamil Nadu and UT of Pondicherry; 5,22,201 SHGs in West Bengal; and 1,11,248 SHGs in Rajasthan were functioning. Efforts by the banks in providing financial services to the poor are being supplemented by NGOs. There are hundreds of NGOs in the country working actively in the formation, nurture and stabilization of self-help groups and in the process of enabling them to be linked to bank finance. Dissatisfaction with the results of many credit programmes has demanded new modalities to provide effective financial service to rural poor. Experiences in various countries have brought to limelight that SHGs play a significant role in mobilizing substantial amount of savings, it is interesting to note that while considering the average amount of disbursement per SHG by the banking sector as a whole commercial banks (50.34 percent) are in the first place, RRBs (38.66 percent) in the second place and co-operative banks (11percent) in the third place respectively.⁴ Initially the SHGs have to pass many hurdles, however the strength of group dynamics and the in-build and interrelated mechanisms of SHG components have made this SHG movement as a successful model.

NGO Linked Self-Help Groups

National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) has formulated the concept of “Mother Non-Governmental Organization”: for the self-help groups during 1999. The formation and strengthening of self-help groups have been the basic philosophy and responsibility of the programme. It has been felt that “if the women have money in their hands” it “leads to better and more dignified lives”. Self-help group promoted self-reliance by generating its own funds rather than remaining in the vicious cycle of debt. This programme aims:

- To enable the poor and marginalized women to have access to micro-credit with the bank linkages through enterprising self-help groups.
- To promote the concept of self-help groups by sensitizing bankers, the government and non-governmental organization.
- To generate awareness among the members of the self-help groups.⁵

Subsequently NGOs play an important role in developing SHG members through capacity building, training and skill development for income generation.

Tamil Nadu Women Development Project (Mahalir Thittam)

Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women (TNCDW) was established in 1983 with an aim to enhance the status of women through education, employment, economic development and self-reliance. It spearheaded the SHG movement in Tamil Nadu and dedicated itself for the progress of women. The relentless effort of TNCDW has been continuing till date to establish an inclusive society in which women are assured of their opportunities on par with men.

On its resounding success, it was named as Mahalir Thittam (MaThi) and was implemented in all districts. TNCDW facilitated the SHGs in financial empowerment and social emancipation. MaThi has now become a powerful movement in the State and the SHG members are very active and vibrant in all walks of life. TNCDW is playing a pivotal role in organizing women into SHGs, providing capacity building, federating them and facilitating credit linkage for income generation activities.⁶

Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women has observed that “Empowerment of one million women in Tamil Nadu with special emphasis on the poorest and disadvantaged is the vision of Mahalir Thittam”. Social empowerment, economic empowerment and capacity building are the mission of the Mahalir Thittam.

NGOs are another important unit that provides quality of work and commitment to this project at the grassroots level. They help to form groups and work continuously with the groups to make them strong, cohesive with and sustainable. They serve as advisor and facilitator to the groups on various matters such as social, economic and community action programmes. In order to understand the activity of the SHG in the frame work of movement, some groups were selected and conducted a focus group interview with them. From the analysis it is found that the self-help groups are organized to manage their economic activities better and are gaining empowerment in directions, which are appropriate to their needs, interests and constraints. They gained confidence from an increase in their relative financial independence and security. The increase in the literacy skills of the SHG members is another indicator of empowerment. Some of them learned to sign, to read and write and could do simple arithmetic work. The animators and representatives and SHG members got trained for this work by the NGOs with the help of Mahalir Thittam officials. The animators and felt that through this one could develop certain leadership qualities such as organizing meetings, liaison with NGOs and Government officials, coordinating and motivating the members.⁷

Training is yet another very important activity under the project. The groups are trained through NGOs and pave the way to create awareness and motivate the members to realize their strengths

and weakness and their potential. Gradually, they become more conscious for their capabilities and start exhibiting them through their action plans and programme. Grading of NGOs working under the project and the Plus are carried out once in 6 months periodically. This is done to identify weak NGOs, with a poor tracks, and to improve the delivery of services to the ultimate beneficiaries. Grading of NGOs assess themselves and submit their reports to PIU. Committee sits with the NGO and assesses the report. Mature groups ready to absorb bank loans are linked with financial institutions to avail credit. Their credit worthiness has been proved beyond doubt and repayment is largely on schedule, with over dues being an exception. The loans are disbursed and recovered through the groups and the groups take responsibility for repayment. In turn, the groups extend credit to the members, after group consensus. The members thus avail loans for income generating activities of their choice. The lending and recovery procedures have thus built in safety in ensuring prompt payment through peer pressure of group members reinforced by “ SHG credit guidelines” and grading of groups which have become streamlined over the years. The major credit sources are Swarnjyanthi Gram Swarojgar Yojana (SGSY), National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development(NABARD), Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK), Non –governmental Organization loan and Swarna Jayanti Shahari Rozgar Yojana (SJSRY).⁸

The main partners of the corporation in social development process are NGOs. It is very important for us to build the capacity of small and medium sized NGOs to enable them to work better for benefit of the self-help groups. Hence, in order to promote active performance by both NGOs and individual volunteer for benefit of society. NGO Volunteer Resource Center (NVRC) is being setup for capacity building of NGOs, volunteer promotion, data exchange, networking and documentation.

Entrepreneurship skill training is being undertaken by several agencies like Tamil Nadu Adi Dravidar Housing & Development Corporation Limited (THADCO), TamilNadu Backward Classed Economic Development Corporation Limited (TABCEDCO), Directorate of Industries and commerce and TNCDW. Government of Tamil Nadu has given a massive thrust for EDP training for women and training. Women who do not possess skill and choose a particular trade during EDP had also been assisted in getting the required skill training. After training assistance is provided for credit linkages with nationalized banks/financial institutions through the respective self-help groups, these trainers in turn train potential entrepreneurs among women’s groups with business and technical skill for women. They help eligible self-help groups to access external credit in close coordination with the Rural Development Department and local banks enabling to become increasingly self-reliant. The development councils also work for convergence service of various departments with self-help groups enabling better services of field-level.⁹

Capacity Building: Marketing Support Exhibition

TNCDW organizes 3 state level exhibitions every year on the eve of Pongal, Chithirai, (Tamil New Year) and Navarathiri occasions as “Mahalir Mela” to popularize and promote the sales of the SHG products like handicrafts, artificial jewellery, jute products, leather goods, millet products etc.

State and District Supply and Marketing Society

The State Supply and Marketing Society (SSMS) has been formed and registered under Tamil Nadu Societies Registration Act, 1975 with an objective of promoting the sale of SHG products at National, State and District levels. All District Supply and Marketing Societies have been linked to the SSMS. In addition to organizing special sales exhibition at State, District and Block level, these societies encourage the SHGs to improve their sales in the competitive market by value addition and attractive packages.

Mathi KIOSK

“Mathi” Kiosk is an exclusive Sale outlets to promote the sale of SHGs products which have been established in urban areas, particularly in tourist places, bus stands, temples, Government offices / institutions. Popular products of SHGs are herbal products, handicrafts, stylish jute products, artificial jewellery, minor millet and handmade toys etc.

Employment Generation and Skill Training

1. Support to SHGs
2. Formation of Fish Marketing Societies
3. Income Generation Activity Training
4. Micro Enterprise Development
5. Vocational Training to Unemployed Youth

Massive Entrepreneurship Development Programme (MEDP)

To cover five lakhs of women within a time span of five years the Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women Ltd., implemented the Massive Entrepreneurship Development Programme during 2001-2002. With the financial assistance rendered by the Commercial Banks, Scheduled Banks, Government and other financial institutions, self-employment opportunities were provided to women, who were members of registered and unregistered self-help groups. With the co-ordination of Rural Development, Agricultural Department, Industries Department, TAHDCO etc., 4,74,254 women were benefited by way of training in vocational sectors such as tailoring, making readymade garments, leather products, radio and T.V repairs, computer training, catering technology, food processing, fish etc.

The Skill Training Programme was launched from 2004-2005. The trained self-help group women gained the capabilities to start their own income generating economic activities. Between 2003 and 2005 nearly 12,500 women members of self-help groups obtained training in entrepreneurial activities. The State and Central Governments, the Norwegian Assistance for Rural Development (NORAD) and Support to Training Employment Programme for Women (STEP) were the funding agencies. Under this scheme the TNCDW Ltd. has arranged training for 30 district and marketing centers.

Tamil Nadu Non-Government Organizations and Voluntary Resources Centre (TNVRS) is a resource centre functioning from 2001, onwards for offering training to the staff of nongovernmental organizations for improving their capacity as well as the quality. These training programmes also enhance the efficiency of the programme such as Mahalir Thittam. They also assist the Non-Government Organisations to monitor the self-help groups effectively in Tamil Nadu. Due to the efforts of such centers 64 percent of the rural women were included in the self-help groups movement.

Tamil Nadu Empowerment and Poverty Reduction Project – Tamil Nadu Puduvalu Society is yet another scheme implemented by the Government of Tamil Nadu for the well being of poor women. Since 1992 Tamil Nadu pioneered the self-help group movement. This movement stands for the social and economic empowerment of women. It has state level as well as district level societies. While the former served as a monitor in the implementation of the scheme the latter one sanctions, the project proposals of the self-help groups and disburses fund according to the financial procedure laid down by the society. It also offers technical assistance to the self-help group.

The Village Level Poverty Reduction Committee is yet another measure which takes efforts to form self-help groups in the rural community. It improves the capacity and efficiency of the already

prevalent self-help groups. It offers proposals for the economic activities of the vulnerable member of the self-help groups.

Thus, the self-help group movement in Tamil Nadu is widened by the various other schemes introduced by the Government of Tamil Nadu for the sake of the enhanced women empowerment. Such schemes are also of immense help in elevating the status of women from their backwardness. The self-help groups are viable alternatives to achieve objectives of rural development and to get community participation in all the rural development programmes.¹⁰

Role of NGO in Madurai District

The experience across the country has shown that group formation and development is not a spontaneous process. A facilitator working closely with the communities at grass root level can play a crucial role in the group formation and development. The quality of the groups can be influenced by the capacity of the facilitator. The facilitator may or may not be an official. In some cases, NGOs not only work as the facilitator but also help in training and capacity building of facilitators being used by District Rural Development Agencies (DRDAs).

SACRED (Social Animation Centre for Rural Empowerment and Development)

Social Animation Centre for Rural Empowerment and Development (SACRED) is a voluntary organization established by a team of committed individuals having the same vision of serving the society. Now the Society is 27 years old in its path of development intervention for the poor and needy from rural and urban areas. Social Animation Centre for Rural Empowerment and Development (SACRED) is working all over the areas in Madurai District especially extending their service territory with 56 villages of Vadipatti, Usilampatti, Chellampatti and Sedapatti Blocks, Madurai District, Tamil Nadu. In all the above villages they have mainly initiated the project related to imparting education to child labour, out of school and drop-out children, developing livelihood skills for youth, supporting the school going children with educational materials, empowering women for improving their social and economic status, promotion of community health and sanitation programmes etc.³⁰

Aims and Objectivities of SACRED

- To financially assist the children by sponsorship programmes.
- To initiate programmes towards women empowerment schemes.
- To provide assistance towards schemes connected with self-employment training and, social education programmes etc.
- To undertake social service activities and to provide facilities for the relief of the poor, irrespective of caste, creed and social status.

Mahalir Thittam Implemented by SACRED

Tamil Nadu Corporation for Development of Women has approved SACRED as the organization to form, train and monitor the women SHG under Mahalir Thittam in Madurai District. All SHGs were encouraged to join Mahalir Thittam to engage in economic activities in order to increase their family income. Further the SHGs availed credit facilities from the banks, and utilize and to involve in various economic activities. SACRED is implementing the Mahalir Thittam schemes in the following 4 blocks i.e., Chellampatti, Usilampatti, Sedapatti and Vadipatti Blocks from Madurai District.

Orientation Training to Women SHG Members

The SHGs are functioning well, but they are lacking in the skills in some areas. They need to improve their capacity in micro enterprises and handicrafts. SACRED provide training for SHG on producing phenol, cleaning materials, artificial flowers toys and so on. They had received training in the past, but due to lack of marketing opportunities they spent their days in idle. Hence they took up on the task of providing the opportunities to produce and market various items of daily use. SACRED also provided them the knowledge on the procurement of raw materials and created linkages with the market so that the selling of the finished product is not a problem for them. 250 women are benefitted through this programme, from the areas of. Chellampatti, Sedapatti and Vadipatti from Madurai District.

Self-Employment Training for Youth Group Members

Self-employment training for youth group members is an important activity. Earlier SACRED has provided them the training on producing phenol, cleaning materials, artificial flowers and garland making, greeting cards making, embroidery, decoration items like golden tree, pet box, toys and so on. Most of the youth group members barrow money in order to tackle their family situations such as family ceremonies, children's education, health issues, and other unexpected expenses. In the past, they had been approaching the money lenders who charged higher rates of interest. Now, through the SHGs they are able to obtain internal loans and repay the same by paying low interest, i.e. 1%. In case of pressing needs on humanitarian basis, some SHGs even provide loans without interest. SACRED acts as a guarantor to obtain loans for women who are identified to be earnest in business enterprises and received training.

Vermi Compost Training to Women SHG Members and Youth SHG Members

All human beings are running towards organic food and organic fruits and organic intakes. Because they are suffered by synthetic agriculture and by the food produced by synthetic fertilizers. Many researches prove that only organic food will be the solution for upcoming the adverse effects of synthetic food from synthetic agriculture. So it is important to give technical inputs to farmers for organic farming to ensure healthy society. SACRED conducted 3 such organic farming awareness programmes for farmers. In this programme, the importance and advantages of organic farming were taught to them. The production of bio-fertilizers like vermi composting, cowdung manure etc. was demonstrated to the farmers. More over the techniques and methodologies were also disseminated in this programme.³¹

Women Empowerment Training

The rural women from their project area are not aware of their own situation they are facing several discrimination like domestic violence, education, employment, right to information, leadership quality, equal wage, etc., so the problems of women were analyzed by the committee members from the point of women empowerment perspective. Therefore, SACRED conducted orientation to 500 rural poor women. The following topics were covered,

- Rural women today
- Historical evaluation of women oppression
- Role of rural women in their own empowerment process
- Government schemes and income generation activities
- Legal protection
- Environment and women
- Health and hygiene

- Rural development
- Microfinance and marketing strategies
- Self-reliance etc.

From the perspective of rural poor women these activities would be great change for them to know about their problems and various development schemes intended to them and to find ways and means to tap the resources from the government side. In order to help rural poor women to know about the development and to learn the nuances of obtaining data from the government. Apart from this SACRED has decided to conduct a range of programmes and services on need basis in time and demand raised from the community. Thus, it is obvious that SACRED is working for the welfare of the needy and poor rural women from the Madurai District.³²

Conclusion

Despite considerable progress of the economy after independence in India, poverty and unemployment remain most burning problems. The experience from the planned development so far is that an outsider cannot tackle the wide spread poverty and unemployment. Rural women need to be organized themselves in to self-help groups to mobilize their own limited savings and use it for their own betterment. After the formation of SHGs the women are in empowerment process and they are in a better position to negotiate with the banks for the loans, take up gainful activity and participate in the marketing of their products to generate income. The SHGs act as a support groups, developing courage, offering mutual solace and comfort to the members. Training programmes on accounts and managerial inputs provide them the availability of credit, leading to set up successful enterprises. This success in turn leads to the growth of their confidence and improves their status at home and in the community. Mahalir Thittam is implemented in partnership with Non-Governmental Organizations who help in formation of SHGs, provide training and monitor them. The NGOs are provided funds and interested NGOs are affiliated as partners to Mahalir Thittam if they satisfy the norms for affiliation. With the changing scenario of marketing, the concept of market has been changed drastically. Customer behavior and competition is also changing in the fast pace with the changes in the market environment. To compete with global scenario small SHGs have to become aggressive and innovative. In case of profits, only promotional techniques adopted by them influence the profitability of their enterprises. SHGs have to understand the concept of marketing strategies through proper marketing choice and effective mix of other marketing elements to get substantial market opportunities.

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